

Fracture Characteristics of Particulate Reinforced Composite using Digital Image Correlation

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Introduction

- Particulate reinforced composites (PRC) has been widely used in the engineering field such as solid rocket fuel, automobile and aerospace industries.
- The crack would expand the combustion area and causes excessive burning pressure, when particulate reinforced composite is used for solid rocket fuel, whereby rocket motor can be damaged and failed because of unexpected pressure.
- It is important to evaluate the characteristic of crack propagation behavior for particulate reinforced composites under various temperatures and load speeds.

Objective

- To investigate crack resistance behavior of particulate reinforced composites, wedge splitting tests were conducted at various load speed and temperature conditions.
- To evaluate crack resistance behavior of PRC, CTOD and CTOA were measured.
- To estimate the strain fields, digital image correlation method was used at various load speed and temperature conditions.
- To analyse fracture mechanisms, SEM images were observed at various temperatures.

Experimental procedures

- Material : Particulate reinforced composite (PRC)
- Geometry of specimen : Wedge splitting test (WST)

- WST method was proposed by Tschegg.
- The loads in the vertical direction are applied to testing tool and the CMOD (Crack mouth opening displacement) is measured
- The value of fracture energy as the area under splitting load-CMOD curve is considered to be equal to the energy dissipated at fracture.
- [Test condition] Temperature : 60°C, Room temperature, -20°C, -40°C, -60°C
Displacement rate : 5, 50, 500 mm/min
- [Equations] $-CMOD = 2d \cdot \tan(\alpha)$ - $F_{sp} = \frac{F_v}{2 \tan(\alpha)}$ - $CTOA = \tan^{-1}(\frac{CTOD}{d})$

Digital image correlation

- The crack tip opening angle (CTOA) is an angle obtained from the crack tip opening displacement.
- The critical CTOA (CTOAc) is obtained in the stable stage of crack propagation. It is considered to be the material fracture resistance.
- Digital image correlation (DIC) system is available to compare full fields of the reference with that of deformed specimen.

Results and discussion

[Results of major strain contour at crack length 3 mm]

- Conclusion
- The splitting load-CMOD, CTOD and CTOA-crack extension curves of particulate reinforced composites significantly depend on displacement rate and temperatures.
- In the wedge Splitting test, as the test speed increases, the stress relaxation phenomenon decreases, and the high stress is left in the specimen.
- As the temperature decreases, CTOD and CTOA increases, however the glass transition behavior at -60°C decreases due to brittle behavior
- As a result of the DIC analysis, the strain increases as the temperature decreases, and the brittle behavior at -60°C shows low strain. As the test speed increases, the strain increases because the stress relaxation phenomenon decreases.